

Synthesis and Biological Properties of 2-Mercaptopyrimido-[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-ones and their S-Alkyl Derivatives

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The synthesis of some hitherto unreported 2-mercaptopyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-ones (4) is described. Treatment with alkyl halides under basic conditions yielded the S-alkyl derivatives. The synthesised compounds are characterised by spectral and analytical data. Most of the compounds of the series exhibit promising antibacterial and antifungal activities.

A number of 4-cinnolyl sulphides and sulphones¹ have been synthesised in view of their potential antibacterial properties. Eisaku *et al.*² described the synthesis of 4-cinnolyl sulphones from 4-cinnolyl sulphides by oxidation with potassium permanganate in acetic acid. Owing to the importance of cinnolyl sulphides as antibacterial agents and the importance of the naturally occurring pyrimidine ring, the synthesis of different 2-mercaptopyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-ones and their alkyl derivatives was carried out with a view to studying their antibacterial activity. This paper describes the synthesis, antibacterial and antifungal screening and the structure-activity relationship studies of the title compounds 4 and 5.

Only scant reports of cinnolines have appeared in the literature because of the large number of steps involved in their synthesis. In the present study, the simple and elegant method of synthesis of 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamides (3) described by Gewald *et al.*³, have been utilised.

Diazonium chloride of amines (1) and cyanoacetamide were reacted in equimolar amounts in presence of sodium acetate to give the required intermediate arylhydrazono(cyano)acetamides⁴ (2) (Scheme 1). Compound 2 was cyclised with anhydrous aluminium chloride in chlorobenzene³. The nitrile group takes part in the cyclisation. Treatment of the aluminium complex with hydrochloric acid liberates

the base hydrochloride from which the free base 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamides (3) were obtained by treatment with aqueous ammonia. Compound 3 was refluxed with potassium *O*-ethylthiocarbonate⁵ in dimethylformamide. The precipitated potassium salt of 2-mercaptopyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-one was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution and acidified to give 2-mercaptopyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-one (4) in good yield. Treatment of 4 with alkyl iodide or ethyl bromoacetate under basic conditions followed by acidification afforded the corresponding 2-(alkylthio)derivatives (5) in good yields.

Biological studies : All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity against the gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cirrflagels* and gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas mandica*. The antifungal activity was tested against the fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*. The cup-plate⁶ method was followed at a concentration of 100 mg ml⁻¹. A 0.1% phenol was used as the standard compound. Most of the compounds showed moderate or maximum antibacterial and antifungal activity (Table 1). Generally the S-alkyl derivatives (5) and in particular, compounds 4d and 5l exhibited higher activities.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries

Scheme 1

and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a Varian mat CH-7 (Finigan mat 8230 GC-MS) and RMU-GL Hitachi spectrometers.

All the solvents were distilled and dried according to the literature procedures. Pre-coated silica gel plates were used for analytical tlc.

Arylhydrazone(cyano)acetamide (2a-d): The diazonium chloride solution was prepared by adding sodium nitrite (1.4 g, 0.02 mol) in water (20 ml) to a solution of the appropriate amine (0.02 mol) in 1 N HCl (100 ml) at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 10 min. The diazotised solution was then added to a well-stirred mixture of cyanoacetamide (1.68 g, 0.02 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and water (400 ml). Sodium acetate was added

in small portions to keep the reaction mixture alkaline to litmus. After 3 h of stirring at 0°, the crude product was filtered, washed with water, air-dried and crystallised from alcohol or aqueous alcohol as yellow crystals (78–85%).

TABLE I—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 5*

Compd No	Antibacterial				Antifungal	
	A	B	C	D	E	F
4a	++	++	++	++	++	+
b	++	++	++	++	++	++
c	+	++	++	++	+	+
d	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5a	+	++	++	++	++	+
b	+++	++	++	+++	+++	++
c	+	++	+	++	++	+
d	++	++	++	++	++	++
e	++	++	++	+++	+++	++
f	+++	++	++	++	++	++
g	+++	++	+++	+++	++	+++
h	++	++	+	++	++	++
i	++	++	+	++	++	+
j	+++	++	++	+++	+++	+++
k	++	++	++	++	++	+
l	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
Standard (0.1% phenol)	++	++	++	++	++	+

*A = *Staphylococcus aureus*, B = *Bacillus cirrflagels*, C = *Escherichia coli*, D = *Pseudomonas mandica*, E = *Aspergillus niger*, F = *Candida albicans*; 11–15 mm (+) = poor inhibition, 16–20 mm (++) = moderate inhibition, 20 mm (+++) = maximum inhibition.

4-Aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide (3a-d) : A mixture of arylhydrazono(cyano)acetamide (25 mmol), chlorobenzene (30 ml) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.6 g, 50 mmol) was stirred for 1 h under gentle reflux. After cooling, the mixture was stirred with 1 : 1HCl (100 ml). The product precipitated on cooling was filtered, dissolved in water (500 ml) and neutralised with ammonia solution. Recrystallisation from dimethylformamide or aqueous dimethylformamide afforded white crystals (58–65%).

2-Mercaptopyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3H)-one

(4a-d) : A mixture of 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide (12 mmol) and potassium-*O*-ethylthiocarbonate (3.8 g, 24 mmol) in dimethylformamide (180 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled in an ice-bath and the resulting solid was dissolved in 1 *N* NaOH, then treated with animal charcoal, filtered and the filtrate acidified with acetic acid to pH 5. The yellow solid was collected, washed with cold water (3 × 25 ml) and dried. It was further purified by dissolving in 1 *N* NaOH and reprecipitated by glacial acetic acid followed by recrystallisation in dimethylformamide to give yellow or red crystals (74–78%). Analytical tlc was performed for checking the purity of the compounds (75–78%) : **4a**, m.p. >350°; *m/z* 230 (*M*⁺); *v*_{max} (KBr) 1 240 (C=S), 1 710 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.49 (1H, s, SH), 7.98–9.16 (4H, m, ArH), 13.08 (1H, s, NH); **4b**, m.p. >350°; **4c**, m.p. 350°; *m/z* 244 (*M*⁺); *v*_{max} (KBr) 1240 (C=S), 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.5 (1H, s, SH), 2.55 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.55–8.65 (3H, m, ArH), 12.6 (1H, s, NH); **4d**, m.p. >350°. The deuterium exchange studies show the disappearance of SH peak at δ 2.5 and NH peak at δ 12.6.

2-Alkylmercaptopyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3H)-one (5a-l) : To a solution of 4 (10 mmol) in 1 *N* NaOH (50 ml) or aqueous Na₂CO₃ (30 ml) was added alkyl iodide or ethyl bromoacetate (12 mmol) respectively and the mixture was stirred vigorously for 2 h at room temperature. The solid separated on acidification (pH 5) with acetic acid was washed with cold water (2 × 50 ml), dried and crystallised from aqueous dimethylformamide to yield the products (70–80%) : **5a**, m.p. 310°, *m/z* 244 (*M*⁺); *v*_{max} (KBr) 1 370 (SCH₃), 1 700 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.65 (3H, s, SCH₃), 7.6–8.5 (4H, m, ArH), 12.9 (1H, s, NH); **b**, m.p. 286°; **c**, m.p. 278°; δ 2.55 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.65 (3H, s, SCH₃), 7.5–8.33 (3H, m, ArH), 12.47 (1H, s, NH); **i**, m.p. 320°; δ 2.75 (2H, s, SCH₂), 2.9 (5H, m, COOC₂H₅), 7.77–8.57 (4H, m, ArH), 12.51 (1H, s, NH).

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